

A multi-agent hierarchical framework for students' risk-aware mental health monitoring. SENTIA: State-Enabled Neuro-symbolic Trajectory-aware Intelligent Architecture

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Abstract: Universities are increasingly confronted with rising levels of student anxiety, stress, sleep disturbances and social anxiety, amplified by academic pressure, digital environments and post-pandemic psychosocial shifts. While digital mental health tools and conversational agents have emerged as scalable support mechanisms, most existing systems rely on opaque large language model (LLM) pipelines, loosely coordinated multi-agent interactions or end-to-end black-box predictions that limit interpretability and reproducibility. Current approaches often lack structured state persistence, deterministic supervisory control, longitudinal distress modeling and transparent risk stratification mechanisms, creating gaps in safety governance and explainable intervention design. Motivated by the need for a clinically aligned, interpretable and modular orchestration framework capable of supporting preventive mental health monitoring in academic environments, our study proposes a hierarchical, state-driven, multi-agent architecture built upon a persistent structured state representation-SENTIA. The objective is to design a deterministic supervisory system in which specialized agents operate over a shared coordination state, ensuring modular reasoning, controlled updates and transparent safety routing. The proposed framework-SENTIA introduces (i) a persistent psychometric-aligned state vector integrating triggers, confidence levels, severity bands, environmental context, longitudinal trajectories and risk signals; (ii) deterministic state-transition functions governing all updates; (iii) a supervisory orchestration layer enforcing sequential agent execution and preventing uncontrolled cross-agent reasoning; (iv) an explicit risk override mechanism for crisis-sensitive scenarios. The evaluation framework combines an external robustness benchmark (*Psych8k*) with a controlled internal simulation of 400 cases to assess both generalization and alignment performance. The simulations demonstrate that augmenting user queries with structured profile information (severity, trigger, risk level) substantially improves system effectiveness. Retrieval performance increases markedly (e.g., Precision@3 from 0.56 to 0.72; nDCG@3 from 0.65 to 0.85), while generation quality improves in terms of domain accuracy (60% to 90%), groundedness (1.0 to 1.55) and reduced hallucination rate (25% to 12%).

Keywords: multi-agent architecture; psychometric state vector; supervisory orchestration; mental health; post-COVID

1. Introduction

The increase in psychological distress among university students has become a critical public health concern, with anxiety, stress-related disorders, sleep disturbances and social anxiety significantly affecting academic performance [1]. Higher education institutions are therefore exploring digital and AI-driven support systems to complement limited counseling resources and provide early detection and preventive monitoring [2], [3], [4], [5]. Advances in large language models (LLMs) and multi-agent architectures have enabled conversational systems capable of nuanced dialogue and adaptive feedback. However, despite their expressive capabilities, most existing AI-based mental health assistants operate as opaque, loosely structured pipelines, often lacking explicit state persistence, deterministic supervisory logic, longitudinal modeling and transparent safety governance mechanisms [6], [7].

The LLM-based systems rely on implicit conversational memory rather than structured, psychometrically grounded state representations, limiting interpretability and reproducibility. Second, multi-agent approaches frequently allow unconstrained cross-agent reasoning, increasing the risk of inconsistent outputs and reducing modular verifiability. Third, longitudinal distress trajectories and severity evolution are rarely modeled through explicit deterministic state transitions, constraining preventive analytics. Finally, safety mechanisms, particularly crisis detection and override logic, are often embedded heuristically rather than implemented as formal, auditable control layers [8]. Such limitations hinder the deployment of AI systems in student mental health, where explainability, reliability and structured risk stratification are essential. Considering them, our paper addresses the following research questions:

(RQ1) How can LLM-based multi-agent systems be architected to ensure deterministic, interpretable and reproducible behavior in mental health applications?

(RQ2) How to incorporate a persistent, structured state representation to improve longitudinal distress monitoring, preventive screening accuracy, safety and diagnostic transparency?

(RQ3) How can explicit risk stratification and crisis override mechanisms be formally embedded within AI-driven support systems for student populations?

We denote the proposed framework as **SENTIA** (State-Enabled Neuro-symbolic Trajectory-aware Intelligent Architecture), a hierarchical, risk-aware multi-agent system built upon a persistent psychometric-aligned state representation. SENTIA advances beyond end-to-end LLM conversational systems by operationalizing a state-centric supervisory AI paradigm for preventive mental health monitoring. Specifically, it operationalizes a structured execution pipeline comprising five cognitive agents (Advisor Specialist, Profiler Agent, Environmental Context Agent, Trend & Predictive Analyst, Differential Pattern Analyst) coordinated by an *Orchestrator* and a Risk Stratification Agent that enforce routing logic and safety overrides. Unlike prior LLM-based mental health assistants that rely primarily on prompt-driven reasoning and implicit conversational memory, SENTIA introduces a fundamentally different architectural paradigm centered on the persistent state representation and deterministic supervisory control in which all cognitive agents read from and write to a shared psychometric-aligned coordination vector, and every update is governed by explicit state-transition functions. Risk stratification and crisis override mechanisms are implemented as rule-based, auditable control layers that precede downstream generation, ensuring safety-critical determinism rather than probabilistic escalation.

The main contributions of the paper are:

- *Persistent psychometric-aligned state representation*-We introduce a structured and longitudinally persistent state vector that serves as the central coordination object for multi-agent mental health systems, enhancing interpretability, traceability and reproducibility.
- *Formal supervisory policy modeling*-We create an explicit state-dependent execution policy governing agent routing and crisis override logic, transforming LLM-based multi-agent coordination into a formally auditable decision process.
- *Formalized risk stratification and crisis governance*-We propose auditable and rule-based crisis override mechanisms within the orchestration layer, ensuring safety-critical responses are governed deterministically rather than emerging from prompt-level heuristics.
- *Longitudinal distress modeling for preventive analytics*-We incorporate structured trajectory modeling and differential pattern analysis to enable early detection, preventive screening and structured severity monitoring across time. The integration of structured longitudinal trajectories within multi-agent LLM systems establishes a preventive analytics framework rather than reactive conversational support.
- *Neuro-symbolic hybrid architecture for mental health AI*-We design a modular framework that integrates symbolic supervisory control with constrained LLM reasoning, positioning SENTIA within the broader class of knowledge-based and expert systems rather than purely generative conversational agents. Although applied to student mental health, the proposed state-centric supervisory architecture provides a transferable design paradigm for safety-critical LLM-based expert systems.

2. Literature review

Early work highlighted the growing mental health burden among university students, particularly during systemic disruptions such as COVID-19, emphasizing the need for targeted institutional and clinical responses to emerging stressors in virtual and socioeconomically unstable environments [9]. Research in Indonesia further demonstrated the development and successful validation of a culturally fine-tuned LLM-based chatbot for university students, achieving substantial gains in accuracy (0.85 accuracy) and high user acceptance (87.38%) [10]. Predictive AI systems such as Jousvex integrated machine learning classification (97% accuracy) with LLM-driven conversational feedback to deliver personalized academic stress assessment and guidance [11]. MindScape extended this direction by integrating passively collected behavioral data with LLM-powered journaling, reporting improvements in positive affect (+7%) and

reductions in anxiety, depression and loneliness over eight weeks [12]. Similarly, MHeVA was designed as a first-line diagnostic virtual assistant in universities and demonstrated strong self-disclosure, rapport-building and student engagement outcomes [13]. Complementing student-focused approaches, research on teacher roles identified four mental health support profiles (connector, awareness raiser, referrer, guardian), emphasizing boundary clarity in higher education contexts [14], while large-scale multilevel analysis in China revealed that teacher positive mental health significantly predicted better student mental health outcomes [15]. Additionally, peer support research identified five distinct intervention types in universities and highlighted engagement and capacity challenges in implementing scalable mental health initiatives [16]. Investigating the psychological impact of LLM overuse, one study found that time-management dependency and social comfort dimensions of LLM addiction significantly increased stress, anxiety and depression, with stronger adverse effects among male students [17]. A global survey of 714 mental health researchers showed widespread LLM adoption (69.5%), particularly for proofreading and coding, while identifying concerns related to inaccuracy ethics, and bias despite reported efficiency gains [18]. Exploring AI-generated qualitative data, researchers found that LLM outputs reproduced dominant stress narratives and stereotypes, underscoring both brainstorming affordances and bias risks in academic research applications [19]. At a broader digital behavior level, clustering analysis of social media usage identified distinct mental health risk profiles, with Instagram showing stronger correlations with anxiety (0.256) and depression (0.186) compared to other platforms [20].

A cross-lingual chatbot (HoMemeTown Dr. CareSam) built on GPT-4.0 demonstrated high user satisfaction (positivity score 9.0/10) and statistically significant advantages over existing tools such as Woebot and Happify, although improvements in personalization and response naturalness were needed [21]. Qualitative interviews with students revealed conditional acceptance of LLMs across care scenarios, highlighting strengths in proactive follow-up and personalization but concerns about emotional depth and training limitations [22]. A pilot LLM-generated prompt game aimed at increasing mental health literacy was perceived as promising by professionals, though narrative oversimplifications required refinement [23]. The “Future Me” chatbot targeted prospection skills and demonstrated effectiveness in facilitating goal clarity (85%) and self-reflection (80%), yet showed limitations in acute stress contexts due to perceived formulaic responses [24]. Evaluating ChatGPT-4o as a voice-based therapist, students reported natural interaction, accessibility and non-judgmental support, but also noted a lack of emotional depth compared to human therapists [25]. A controlled simulation study of ChatGPT-4 in school-counseling dialogues found high warmth (97.5%) and empathy (94.2%) with moderate response stability (0.59) [26]. A Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)-based academic stress chatbot using GPT-3.5 Turbo combined SVM cognitive distortion detection (85.94% accuracy) with intent classification to deliver personalized coping strategies [27]. A randomized controlled trial on a personalizable psychotherapy chatbot showed that personalization significantly increased therapeutic bond, comparable to human therapist relationships, though it did not affect usage intention [28]. LLM-Therapist, employing retrieval-augmented generation with multimodal patient data, demonstrated improved efficiency and response relevance in personalized mental health assistance [29].

To address privacy constraints in mental health AI development, a dual-instance Llama 3.3:70B framework generated demographically realistic synthetic patient interviews with high lexical diversity and demographic representativeness [30]. Finally, advances in non-invasive multimodal emotion recognition, leveraging facial expressions, speech and language through deep learning and transformer architectures, demonstrate growing capabilities for affect detection [31]. Furthermore, [32] reviewed popular commercial mental health chatbot apps through qualitative analysis of user reviews, finding that while users valued their personalized, judgment-free and always-available support, limitations in crisis detection, inappropriate responses and risks of overreliance highlighted the need for better customization, safeguards and balanced use alongside human support. Another study evaluated the feasibility, acceptability and preliminary effectiveness of the AI chatbot Wayhaven among college students with elevated depression or anxiety symptoms [33]. MentalRAG is a multi-agent agentic system that automates patient data collection and analysis for mental health professionals using privacy-preserving local models and advanced LLMs [34]. A brief comparison of previous studies is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparative overview of studies on LLMs, AI and student mental health

Ref.	Objective	Methods	Brief findings	Provides counseling?
[9]	Examine COVID-19 impact on college student mental health	Conceptual/narrative analysis	Pandemic intensified stressors; need for adaptive mental health strategies	-No (conceptual discussion)
[10]	Develop LLM chatbot for Indonesian students	Development+evaluation (n=58)	Accuracy improved to 0.85; 87% acceptance	+Yes (chatbot support)
[11]	Develop AI tool predicting academic stress (Jousvex)	MLP (97% accuracy) + LLM interface	Accurate stress prediction+personalized feedback	+Yes (AI assistant)
[12]	Develop contextual AI journaling app (MindScape)	8-week study (n=20)	Reduced anxiety, depression, loneliness; PHQ-4 decreased	+Yes (AI journaling support)
[13]	Create MHeVA mental health virtual assistant	User study	High engagement, self-disclosure, acceptance	+Yes (virtual assistant)
[14]	Examine teacher role perceptions in student mental health	Survey (n=180), factor analysis	Identified 4 role profiles; boundary issues important	-No
[15]	Assess association between teacher & student mental health	Large-scale multilevel regression (n≈130k students)	Teacher positive mental health linked to better student outcomes	-No
[16]	Define types of peer support in universities	Qualitative interviews (n=16 staff)	Identified 5 peer support models; implementation challenges	-/+Peer support (human-based)
[17]	Test impact of LLM addiction on student mental health (gender moderation)	Survey (n=750), PLS-SEM	LLM overdependence increased stress, anxiety, depression; stronger effects for males	-No
[18]	Assess LLM adoption in mental health research	Global survey (n=714)	69.5% use LLMs; efficiency gains but ethical/accuracy concerns	-No
[19]	Explore LLM-generated qualitative data in engineering education	Comparative content analysis	LLMs reproduce stress narratives; bias risks	-No
[20]	Cluster social media usage & mental health risk	Clustering+RF/XGB (Acc=0.993)	Instagram linked to anxiety/depression clusters	-No
[21]	Develop cross-lingual GPT-4 chatbot for Korean students	Mixed-method pilot (n=20)	High satisfaction (9.0/10 positivity); needs better personalization	+Yes (chatbot support)
[22]	Explore student perspectives on LLM use in mental health scenarios	Pilot interviews (n=10)	Conditional acceptance; concerns about emotional depth	-No (exploratory)
[23]	Test LLM-generated prompt game for mental health literacy	Pilot with 5 professionals, interviews	Potential tool; narrative oversimplifications noted	-/+Partial (educational tool)
[24]	Evaluate “Future Me” prospection chatbot	2 qualitative studies (n=34 total)	Effective for goal clarity (85%); weaker in acute stress	+Yes (guided support)
[25]	Assess ChatGPT-4o as therapist (voice-based)	UTAUT framework study	Natural interaction; lacks emotional depth vs humans	+Yes (AI therapist simulation)
[26]	Evaluate ChatGPT-4 counseling simulations	NLP-based emotion&stability analysis	97.5% warmth; moderate reliability (0.59)	-/+Simulated counseling
[27]	Develop CBT-based GPT chatbot for academic stress	GPT-3.5+SVM (85.94% accuracy)	Effective cognitive distortion detection	+Yes (CBT chatbot)
[28]	Test personalizable psychotherapy chatbot	RCT (n=54)	Personalization increased therapeutic bond	+Yes (chatbot therapy)
[29]	Propose LLM-Therapist using RAG	System development+experiments	Improved personalization and response relevance	+Yes (LLM therapist)
[30]	Generate synthetic patient interviews using Llama 3.3	Dual-LLM simulation framework	Realistic demographic and lexical diversity	-No (training framework)

[31]	Review multimodal recognition	non-invasive emotion	Comprehensive review	literature	Multimodal AI improves affect detection; ethical challenges	-No
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These systems lack either structured state persistence, deterministic supervisory control, longitudinal distress modeling or transparent risk stratification mechanisms. In contrast to prior work focused primarily on conversational fluency and user perception metrics, our study proposes a clinically aligned, hierarchical, state-driven multi-agent architecture grounded in a persistent psychometric-aligned coordination state and deterministic state-transition functions. The proposed framework advances the field from conversational assistance toward interpretable, modular and safety-governed preventive mental health monitoring in academic environments.

3. Methodology

3.1 Hierarchical risk-aware multi-agent architecture

SENTIA is designed as a hierarchical, state-driven, multi-agent orchestration framework wherein specialized agents operate over a shared, structured state vector that contains relevant data for student psychological profile. The architecture consists of three distinct layers (Figure 1): the *Cognitive Layer*, containing five agents responsible for managing user interactions, computing metrics, and establishing student profiles and behavioral patterns; the *Knowledge Layer*, which contains embedded documents related to mental health, including self-help guides from the NHS, NICE, and university sources; and the *Safety & Orchestration Layer*, incorporating two agents tasked with risk management and overall orchestration.

The agents operate under supervisory control to permanently update the vector state:

- *Profiler Agent (PA)* extracts event triggers and questionnaire-aligned constructs using hybrid LLM extraction and deterministic scoring.
- *Environmental Context Agent (ECA)* encodes academic contextual modifiers (e.g., exams, presentations).
- *Trend & Predictive Analyst (TPA)* computes trajectory metrics and linguistic markers from conversations.
- *Advisor Specialist (AS)* manages the user utterance and Q&A sessions and conversations.
- *Differential Pattern Analyst (DPA)* flags possible co-occurring patterns (without diagnosing), producing ranked, non-diagnostic pattern hypotheses for clinicians’ intervention.
- *Risk Stratification Agent (RSA)* detects crisis signals (suicidal ideation, self-harm, acute distress) and override conditions and computes risk levels: low, medium, high and critical.
- *Orchestrator* maintains and updates structured state vector S_t , detects contradictions among agent outputs and resolves logical conflicts and ensures severity-consistent recommendations. It also enforces system boundaries (no diagnosis, no medication advice, no out-of-scope recommendations) and selects downstream agents (AS, PA, TPA, DPA) to generate the system output. The orchestration policy is defined as:

$$\pi(S_t, R_t) \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_t \tag{1}$$

where $\mathcal{A}_t \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is the subset of activated agents and R_t is the risk level computed by the RSA. If risk level is critical ($R_t = 3$), the crisis overrides all other routing decisions and alerts clinicians.

The framework enforces strict functional LLM-deterministic separation: LLM components are used only for structured trigger extraction and questionnaire-aligned semantic parsing in the PA and retrieval-augmented synthesis in the AS; all scoring, aggregation, severity mapping, trend detection, and risk decisions are deterministic. Thus, architecture minimizes hallucination risk, ensures auditability and allows formal verification of system behavior.

Figure 1. Hierarchical state-driven multi agent architecture for preventive student mental health support

3.2 Cognitive layer

3.2.1 Profiler Agent (PA) with standardized psychometric-aligned modules

The PA extracts discrete event triggers τ_t using a constrained LLM-based structured parser $\mathcal{L}_E^k(u_t)$ that processes the user utterance u_t at time t :

$$\tau_t = \mathcal{L}_E^k(u_t) \quad (2)$$

Trigger extraction is restricted to explicitly stated events that are temporally anchored and associated with emotional change. The update of the persistent trigger state (or triggers history) follows deterministic aggregation:

$$\mathcal{H}_t = \mathcal{H}_{t-1} \oplus \tau_t \quad (3)$$

where \oplus merges recurring triggers by incrementing mention count and updating average intensity. No implicit event inference is permitted; absence of explicit event description results in \emptyset . Each trigger τ_t include a set of features such as category (e.g., academic, relationship, health), an optional subtype, a neutral description, the emotional intensity, the mention count, a confidence score, cognitive patterns (e.g., catastrophizing, overgeneralization, self-blame, hopelessness, black and white thinking) and protective factors (e.g., social support, motivation, resilience, help seeking). Based on the user's utterance, the average intensity (\bar{i}_τ^t) and mention count (ϑ_τ^t) are updated for each trigger type:

$$\bar{i}_\tau^t = \frac{(\vartheta_\tau^{t-1} \cdot \bar{i}_\tau^{t-1}) + i_\tau^t}{\vartheta_\tau^{t-1} + 1} \quad (4)$$

PA then computes a normalized *trigger burden index* T_t , defined based on the active triggers, their intensity and mention count:

$$T_t = \frac{1}{n_\tau} \sum_{\tau=1}^{n_\tau} (\bar{i}_\tau^t \cdot \log(1 + \vartheta_\tau^t)) \quad (5)$$

where n_τ is the number of active triggers.

After trigger extraction, PA estimates structured psychological state variables from conversational input using questionnaire-aligned measurement modules. Rather than administering standardized psychometric screening instruments with self-report scales, the system incrementally reconstructs item-level responses through natural language and targeted clarification, thereby preserving conversational flow while maintaining psychometric grounding.

Let us define the set of profiling modules as $\mathcal{M} = \{M_{\text{anx}}, M_{\text{stress}}, M_{\text{sleep}}, M_{\text{soc}}\}$ corresponding to generalized anxiety, perceived stress, insomnia severity and social anxiety. The profiling modules are construct-aligned with validated psychometric screening instruments: Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD-7), Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), Insomnia Severity Index (ISI) and Social Phobia Inventory (SPIN), ensuring standardized and reproducible severity estimation. Each module M_k maintains an item response vector r^k , a module score and a confidence estimator. Formally, each module is expressed as:

$$M_k: (S_{t-1}, u_t) \rightarrow (\text{Score}_k, C_k, r^k, q_{t+1}) \quad (6)$$

where: Score_k is the module score, C_k is the module confidence, r^k is the updated item vector, q_{t+1} is an optional clarification question selected to reduce uncertainty.

The PA performs semantic extraction using the constrained LLM parser and identifies referenced symptom constructs, explicit frequency or severity markers, temporal qualifiers (e.g., “last two weeks”). The LLM is not permitted to infer frequency if it is not explicitly stated. Missing items remain undefined (\emptyset). The item vector is permanently updated through the conversation:

$$r^k \leftarrow r^k \oplus \mathcal{L}_E^k(u_t) \quad (7)$$

Module scoring is strictly deterministic using a mapping function $g_k(r^k)$ that scores each item vector aligned with the psychometric screening instruments:

$$\text{Score}_k = g_k(r^k) \quad (8)$$

Confidence is defined as:

$$C_k = \frac{|\{i: r_i^k \neq \emptyset\}|}{n_k} \quad (9)$$

where n_k is the number of items in module k .

a) **Anxiety module** (M_{anx}) reconstructs seven items (constructs) aligned with generalized anxiety domains: $r^{\text{anx}} = (r_1^{\text{anx}}, \dots, r_7^{\text{anx}})$, $r_j^{\text{anx}} \in \{0,1,2,3\} \cup \{\emptyset\}$ where each item corresponds to constructs such as nervousness, uncontrollable worry, excessive worry, trouble relaxing, restlessness, irritability and fear of negative outcomes. Responses follow a standard frequency scale: $\{0 = \text{not at all}, 1 = \text{several days}, 2 = \text{more than half the days}, 3 = \text{nearly every day}\}$. If an item is mentioned but frequency is unspecified, the system issues a single clarification probe (e.g., “*Over the last two weeks, has this happened several days, more than half the days, or nearly every day?*”).

b) **Stress module** (M_{stress}) models perceived controllability and overload using ten construct-aligned items: $r^{\text{stress}} = (r_1^{\text{stress}}, \dots, r_{10}^{\text{stress}})$, $r_j^{\text{stress}} \in \{0,1,2,3,4\} \cup \{\emptyset\}$. Items include perceived lack of control, difficulties piling up, feeling overwhelmed and two reverse-coded appraisal constructs. Responses follow: $\{0 = \text{never}, 1 = \text{almost never}, 2 = \text{sometimes}, 3 = \text{fairly often}, 4 = \text{very often}\}$.

c) **Sleep module** (M_{sleep}) models insomnia-related impairment across seven constructs: $r^{\text{sleep}} = (r_1^{\text{sleep}}, \dots, r_7^{\text{sleep}})$, $r_j^{\text{sleep}} \in \{0,1,2,3,4\} \cup \{\emptyset\}$. Items include difficulty initiating sleep, maintaining sleep, dissatisfaction, daytime impairment and distress. Response scale is: $\{0 = \text{none}, 1 = \text{mild}, 2 = \text{moderate}, 3 = \text{severe}, 4 = \text{very severe}\}$.

d) **Social anxiety module** (M_{soc}) include six evaluation-focused constructs: $r^{\text{soc}} = (r_1^{\text{soc}}, \dots, r_6^{\text{soc}})$, $r_j^{\text{soc}} \in \{0,1,2,3,4\} \cup \{\emptyset\}$. Domains include fear of being judged, avoidance, public speaking anxiety, embarrassment concerns and physical symptoms in social contexts. Severity bands for the reduced SPIN-aligned module are proportionally derived from the 0–4 response scale and do not represent formal diagnostic cutoffs. To reduce overlap with generalized anxiety, trigger-based weighting is applied: $\text{trigger} \in \{\text{presentation, social, dating, group work}\} \Rightarrow \text{increase relevance of } M_{\text{soc}}$.

For each module $k \in \{\text{anx}, \text{stress}, \text{sleep}, \text{soc}\}$, let’s define a band-to-severity mapping function σ_k that converts each module’s score into a normalized ordinal severity level $\sigma_k \in \{0,1,2,3\}$ where 0=minimal/low/subthreshold; 1=mild; 2=moderate; 3=severe/high. Table 2 indicates the scoring and severity bands of the modules aligned with standardized psychological screening scales.

Table 2. Correspondence between modules, standardized psychological screening scales and severity bands

Module	Standardized psychological screening scales	Score	Severity bands
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M_{anx}	GAD-7, 0–21	$Score_{anx} = \sum_{j=1}^7 r_j^{anx}$	$\sigma_{anx} = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq Score_{anx} < 5 \\ 1 & 5 \leq Score_{anx} < 10 \\ 2 & 10 \leq Score_{anx} < 15 \\ 3 & 15 \leq Score_{anx} \leq 21 \end{cases}$
M_{stress}	PSS-10, 0–40	$Score_{stress} = \sum_{j=1}^{10} r_j^{stress}$	$\sigma_{stress} = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq Score_{stress} < 14 \\ 1 & 14 \leq Score_{stress} < 20 \\ 2 & 20 \leq Score_{stress} < 27 \\ 3 & 27 \leq Score_{stress} \leq 40 \end{cases}$
M_{sleep}	ISI, 0–28	$Score_{sleep} = \sum_{j=1}^7 r_j^{sleep}$	$\sigma_{sleep} = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq Score_{sleep} < 8 \\ 1 & 8 \leq Score_{sleep} < 15 \\ 2 & 15 \leq Score_{sleep} < 22 \\ 3 & 22 \leq Score_{sleep} \leq 28 \end{cases}$
M_{soc}	SPIN reduced, 0–24	$Score_{soc} = \sum_{j=1}^6 r_j^{soc}$	$\sigma_{soc} = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq Score_{soc} < 8 \\ 1 & 8 \leq Score_{soc} < 16 \\ 3 & 16 \leq Score_{soc} \leq 24 \end{cases}$

The PA computes a *composite burden index* (B_t) based on the normalized scores with a set of weights $\sum_k w_k = 1$:

$$B_t = \sum_k w_k \cdot \tilde{s}_k^t \quad (10)$$

where the normalized scores are:

$$\tilde{s}_{anx}^t = \frac{Score_{anx}}{21}, \tilde{s}_{stress}^t = \frac{Score_{stress}}{40}, \tilde{s}_{sleep}^t = \frac{Score_{sleep}}{28}, \tilde{s}_{soc}^t = \frac{Score_{soc}}{24} \quad (11)$$

For simulations, the following values are considered: $w_{anx} = 0.35$, $w_{stress} = 0.25$, $w_{sleep} = 0.25$ and $w_{soc} = 0.15$.

To balance psychometric burden and event-trigger pressure, PA calculates a *distress index* D_t :

$$D_t = \gamma_B \cdot B_t^p + \gamma_T \cdot T_t + \gamma_{BT} \cdot B_t \cdot T_t \quad (12)$$

In the implementation, $\gamma_B = 0.55$, $\gamma_T = 0.40$ and $\gamma_{BT} = 0.25$. This weighting ensures that most of the distress trajectory remains anchored in validated psychometric signals (approximately 55%), while trigger burden contributes both directly and through interaction effects. The nonlinear scaling term prevents compression at higher severity levels and allows clinically significant escalation when psychometric vulnerability and contextual stressors coincide. To prevent compression of high-severity cases under a purely linear formulation, psychometric burden is transformed using a mild convex exponent (p). An exponent of $p = 1.2$ is selected as the minimal nonlinear adjustment that expanded the upper-range dynamic range without destabilizing moderate cases or inflating low-severity distress. Sensitivity testing indicated that larger exponents (e.g., 1.5 or 2.0) overly suppressed mid-range burden and distorted calibration boundaries.

For each module k , PA provides a vector state $x_k^t = \{Score_k, C_k, \sigma_k, \tilde{s}_k^t\}$. Finally, the profiler outputs $X_{PA}^t = \{\mathcal{H}_t, \mathcal{M}_t, B_t, T_t, D_t\}$, where $\mathcal{M}_t = \{x_k^t\}$

3.2.2 Environmental Context Agent (ECA)

The ECA models exogenous academic and temporal factors that may influence students' psychological states. Unlike the other cognitive agents that operate directly on conversational input, the ECA processes structured contextual signals derived from institutional calendars and temporal data provided by clinicians or students. Its objective is to differentiate endogenous psychological patterns from context-driven fluctuations, improving interpretability, trend prediction and differential reasoning. Formally, at time t , the ECA receives contextual input E_t from the academic context and produces a structured feature vector:

$$\{exam_t, asses_t, phase_t, semp_t, weekday_t, season_t\} = f_{ECA}^t(E_t) \quad (13)$$

Each component captures a distinct dimension of academic or temporal influence. The exam proximity $exam_t \in [0,1]$ models anticipatory stress dynamics by encoding temporal distance to the nearest examination. It is defined as a smooth decay function of days until the exams, enabling gradual modeling of exam-related anxiety buildup. Complementarily, assessment density $asses_t \in [0,1]$ measures the concentration of deadlines, presentations or major evaluations within a predefined time window (e.g., seven days). It captures workload clustering effects, which are empirically associated with stress escalation

beyond single-event proximity. The categorical variable $phase_t$ represents the academic phase (e.g., regular instruction, midterm period, final examination period, holiday or break). This contextual phase is used to interpret distress signals: elevated stress during finals may reflect situational overload, whereas similar scores during holidays indicate non-academic drivers. The semester progression $semp_t \in [0,1]$ encodes cumulative academic fatigue by representing the relative position within the semester timeline. It models gradual burnout-like trajectories that intensify toward term completion. Temporal rhythm factors are also incorporated. The weekday variable $weekday_t \in \{1, \dots, 7\}$ captures weekly stress cyclicity (e.g., Sunday anticipatory anxiety). The categorical season variable $season_t \in \{winter, spring, summer, autumn\}$ accounts for broader temporal influences such as seasonal mood variability.

Based on these features, ECA computes the *academic load index* (A_t) defined as a weighted function based on the environmental features:

$$A_t = \alpha_1 exam_t + \alpha_2 asses_t + \alpha_3 \mathbb{I}(phase_t \in \{midterm, final\}) + \alpha_4 semp_t \quad (14)$$

where α is a set of weights: $\alpha_1 = 0.4$ (exam proximity), $\alpha_2 = 0.3$ (deadline clustering), $\alpha_3 = 0.1$ (phase boost), $\alpha_4 = 0.2$ (semester fatigue).

Also, a binary *academic-driven indicator* ($e_t \in \{0,1\}$) is computed:

$$e_t = \mathbb{I}(A_t \geq \epsilon) \quad (15)$$

The ECA outputs $X_{ECA}^t = \{A_t, e_t\}$ and relies exclusively on institutional and temporal metadata rather than personal behavioral surveillance.

3.2.3 Trend & Predictive Analyst (TPA)

The TPA models the trajectory of student wellbeing over time by actively monitoring the user interactions. It operates on the longitudinal sequence of profiled event triggers and module scores and outputs a short-horizon trend label (improving/stable/worsening) and an early-warning flag for potential deterioration. TPA does not perform crisis escalation, it provides proactive signals that can trigger additional check-ins, adapt intervention intensity or notify the clinician dashboard.

A *smoothed distress index* is computed using an exponentially weighted moving average on the distress index and academic load index (A_t):

$$\bar{D}_t = \beta \bar{D}_{t-1} + (1 - \beta) \cdot clip(D_t(1 + \lambda \cdot A_t), 0, 1) \quad (16)$$

where $\beta \in (0,1)$ is a weight set empirically to $\beta = 0.5$ and $\lambda \in [0,1]$ set to 0.6. This gives moderate inertia to past states while still allowing the system to react within a few turns (interactions). The trend horizon is defined as $h = 3$ observation steps (e.g., three conversational turns or three daily check-ins). This short window is sufficient to detect the *directional change* $\Delta \bar{D}_t$ without requiring long interaction histories, which is appropriate for student use patterns:

$$\Delta \bar{D}_t = \bar{D}_t - \bar{D}_{t-h} \quad (17)$$

and it is mapped to a *discrete trend label*:

$$Trend_t = \begin{cases} \text{worsening} & \Delta \bar{D}_t \geq \theta_T \\ \text{improving} & \Delta \bar{D}_t \leq -\theta_T \\ \text{stable} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where θ_T is a trend sensitivity threshold set empirically to 0.1 on the normalized distress scale $\bar{D}_t \in [0,1]$. Thus, a change of 10% over the window h is considered clinically meaningful for trend labeling. Smaller fluctuations are treated as noise and labeled “stable”. If confidence is low in the recent window, the trend is marked uncertain and the *Orchestrator* requests one clarifying probe rather than predicting.

TPA extracts the linguistic markers from the user utterances. Based on recent conversations, it aggregates three normalized conversational components: i) emotional negativity $E(u_t)$ captures affective tone intensity and is computed as the mean activation of emotional markers (e.g., hopelessness, exhaustion, fear intensity, anhedonia); ii) cognitive distortion intensity $C(u_t)$ reflects maladaptive thinking patterns (e.g., absolutist language, catastrophic phrasing, negation density) and is computed as the mean activation across distortion-related features; iii) severity-indicator strength $S(u_t)$ measures functional impairment and crisis-related language (e.g., chronicity cues, loss-of-control statements, impairment expressions). Each

component is normalized to the interval $[0,1]$ and defined as the mean activation within its respective feature family. The overall *linguistic severity score* L_t is computed as:

$$L_t = l_1 \cdot E(u_t) + l_2 \cdot C(u_t) + l_3 \cdot S(u_t) \quad (19)$$

The weights $l = \{0.4, 0.3, 0.3\}$ reflect the relative functional roles of conversational features in early distress detection. Emotional negativity is assigned a slightly higher weight (0.4) due to its sensitivity as an early-warning indicator of vulnerability in conversational settings. The weights of the cognitive distortion intensity and severity-indicator strength are equal (0.3 each), indicating their complementary roles in capturing maladaptive reasoning patterns and functional impairment signals. Domain specificity features are also extracted from conversations to identify the topical focus of distress (academic, social, health, existential) and to support differential pattern interpretation and retrieval conditioning. However, they are intentionally excluded from the linguistic severity score because domain mention frequency is not a direct indicator of severity and may conflate topical salience with risk intensity.

Finally, the TPA emits an early *warning flag* W_t if either the distress index crosses a high threshold θ_D or its slope is persistently positive, or linguistic severity score exceeds the threshold θ_L :

$$W_t = \mathbb{I}(D_t \geq \theta_D) \vee \mathbb{I}(\Delta \bar{D}_t \geq \theta_T \wedge \Delta \bar{D}_{t-1} \geq \theta_T) \vee (L_t > \theta_L) \quad (20)$$

For early-warning activation, the linguistic threshold is set to $\theta_L = 0.6$ and the high-distress threshold is set to $\theta_D = 0.3$. This means that when the distress index exceeds 30% of its theoretical maximum, the system triggers a preventive monitoring flag. Additionally, sustained positive slopes (i.e., $\Delta \bar{D}_t \geq \theta_T$ for two consecutive windows) also activate early-warning status, ensuring that gradual escalation is captured even if the absolute distress level has not yet crossed the high threshold. The warning flag schedules PA for daily monitoring to periodically evaluate the user state.

TPA returns a structured object $X_{TPA}^t = \{\bar{D}_t, \Delta \bar{D}_t, Trend_t, W_t, L_t\}$ and targets the clinician monitoring dashboard rather than the student directly.

3.2.4 Advisor Specialist (AS) with RAG-based implementation

The AS is responsible for generating evidence-grounded psychoeducational and intervention-oriented responses based exclusively on a curated corpus of clinical guidelines and scientifically validated resources. Unlike a general-purpose language model, AS does not rely on parametric knowledge alone; instead, it operates under a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) paradigm in which all substantive recommendations must be supported by retrieved textual evidence. The aim is to reduce hallucination risk and ensure traceability of guidance to established sources, such as: CBT manuals, insomnia intervention frameworks and student mental-health best practices and self-help guides.

Rather than manually annotating guideline documents with severity labels or intervention intensity levels, we adopt a query-centric control strategy. The system does not tag documents by severity; instead, it shapes the retrieval query in a severity-aware manner so that semantic similarity in the embedding space naturally prioritizes intervention-appropriate material. In other words, personalization is achieved through controlled query reformulation rather than document filtering. For example, instead of issuing a generic query such as “*CBT for anxiety*”, the system reformulates the request based on the user’s severity profile into a more specific and intensity-aligned query, such as “*simple grounding techniques for mild exam-related anxiety in university students*”. This formulation biases the embedding search toward psychoeducational and brief coping-oriented content, while implicitly reducing the likelihood of retrieving general CBT protocols.

To align retrieval with user psychological burden, let’s define a deterministic query transformation function that conditions retrieval queries on computed scores. It determines the set of active modules M_k^t and applies a deterministic severity-to-language mapping policy $\psi_k(\sigma_k, \tau_t, L_t)$ that augments the retrieval query according to module severity bands, linguistic markers and the most recent trigger τ_t . The mapping ensures alignment between the user’s psychological burden and the complexity of the recommended interventions. The risk levels are also added to the query to inform the AS about the user state. Thus, for each active module $k \in M_k^t$, the final query is enhanced as follows:

$$Q_t^{enhanced} = u_t \oplus R_t \oplus \sum_{k \in M_k^t} \psi_k(\sigma_k, \tau_t, L_t) \quad (21)$$

Given the enhanced query $Q_t^{enhanced}$ and the set of medical documents \mathcal{D} , the advisor retrieves a subset of relevant documents (\mathcal{D}_k) for the active modules. The system response X_{AS}^t is generated by conditioning the LLM on the user context, current state and the top- k retrieved evidence chunks: $X_{AS}^t = \mathcal{L}_k^t(S_t, \mathcal{D}_k, Q_t^{enhanced})$. The LLM generation is constrained to synthesize and rephrase retrieved material rather than introduce unsupported clinical claims. Each recommendation is therefore grounded in verifiable guideline content, and citation identifiers are logged for auditability. The AS operates within scope boundaries enforced by the *Orchestrator*. It does not provide diagnoses, medication advice or crisis intervention directives. When severity levels are elevated to medium or high, it includes language encouraging consultation with a qualified professional, but escalation decisions (critical risk) remain governed by the RSA.

3.2.5 Differential Pattern Analyst (DPA)

The DPA acts as a structured pattern-recognition module that identifies potential overlapping symptom clusters based on questionnaire-aligned profiling scores and linguistic severity scores. The DPA does not generate diagnoses, instead, it produces a ranked list of plausible symptom patterns that may warrant further exploration by a psychologist. The objective is to reduce cognitive bias in downstream interpretation by highlighting alternative explanations consistent with the observed symptom structure.

The DPA evaluates four predefined symptom patterns commonly observed in university student populations: (1) generalized anxiety-dominant, (2) social anxiety-dominant, (3) stress overload, (4) sleep-driven. For each pattern k , DPA computes a continuous pattern score $P_k^t \in [0,1]$ based on the student's state S_t :

$$P_k^t = \rho \cdot \left[\sum_{i=1}^6 \omega_i \cdot f_i(S_t) \right] \quad (22)$$

where $\rho = 1.5$ is a calibration coefficient to account for conservative baseline scoring, ω_i are empirically tuned component weights summing to unity, $f_i(S_t)$ are normalized scoring functions for the following data sources:

1. Primary module score ($\omega_1 = 0.45$) represents the normalized score from the pattern's primary symptom assessment module k (e.g., GAD-7 for generalized anxiety):

$$f_1(S_t) = \tilde{s}_k^t \cdot C_k \quad (23)$$

2. Secondary module scores ($\omega_2 = 0.20$) represent the average of related symptom domains that provide supporting evidence:

$$f_2(S_t) = \frac{1}{|N_k|} \sum_{m \in N_k} \tilde{s}_m^t \quad (24)$$

where N_k is the set of secondary modules for pattern k (e.g., stress and sleep for generalized anxiety).

3. Cognitive pattern markers ($\omega_3 = 0.10$) express the presence of pattern-specific cognitive distortions assessed on 10-point Likert scales:

$$f_3(S_t) = \frac{1}{|cog_k|} \sum_{p \in cog_k} \frac{I_p(S_t)}{10} \quad (25)$$

where cog_k denotes cognitive markers relevant to pattern k (e.g., catastrophizing, fortune-telling for anxiety patterns) and $I_p(S_t) \in [0,10]$ quantifies the intensity of cognitive pattern p .

4. Linguistic markers ($\omega_4 = 0.15$) express deterministic text-based features extracted from conversational data using lexicon matching:

$$f_4(S_t) = \frac{1}{|lng_k|} \sum_{\ell \in lng_k} \text{score}_\ell(u_t) \quad (26)$$

where lng_k represents pattern-specific linguistic indicators (e.g., hopelessness language for depression-like patterns) and score_ℓ computes normalized lexicon overlap ratios for linguistic feature ℓ .

5. Trigger relevance ($\omega_5 = 0.05$) is the alignment between active triggers τ_t and pattern-relevant trigger categories τ_k :

$$f_5(S_t) = \frac{\sum_{\tau_t} I_\tau(S_t)}{\sum_{\tau_k} I_\tau(S_t)} \quad (27)$$

where $I_\tau(S_t)$ is the intensity of trigger τ at time t .

6. Academic load ($\omega_6 = 0.05$) represents the academic load index:

$$f_6(S_t) = A_t \quad (28)$$

A pattern hypothesis is considered clinically meaningful if $P_k^t \geq \varepsilon_k$, where $\varepsilon_k = 0.15$ for all patterns. Multiple patterns may exceed threshold simultaneously, reflecting comorbid presentations common in student populations. The DPA ranks patterns by descending score, designating the highest-scoring pattern as primary for intervention prioritization. The DPA outputs the symptom-pattern hypotheses: $X_{DPA}^t = \{\mathcal{P}_t\}$ where $\mathcal{P}_t = \{P_k^t\}$.

The algorithms of the cognitive agents (ECA, PA, AS, TPA and DPA) are expressed as pseudocode in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1. Cognitive Agents
<p>1. Environmental Context Agent (ECA) Input: Academic context E_t, weights α Step 1. Encode contextual features: $\{exam_t, asses_t, phase_t, semp_t, weekday_t, season_t\} \leftarrow f_{ECA}(E_t)$ Step 2. Compute academic load index: $A_t = \alpha_1 \times exam_t + \alpha_2 \times asses_t + \alpha_3 \times phase_t + \alpha_4 \times semp_t$ Step 3. Compute academic-driven indicator: IF $A_t \geq \epsilon$ THEN $e_t \leftarrow 1$ ELSE $e_t \leftarrow 0$ END IF Output: $X_{ECA}^t = \{A_t, e_t\}$</p>
<p>2. Profiler Agent (PA) Input: utterance u_t, score weights w, distress index weights $\gamma_B, \gamma_T, \gamma_{BT}$, trigger history \mathcal{H}_{t-1}, LLM configuration \mathcal{L}_E^k Step 1. Extract explicit triggers and items for each module k: $\tau_t, r^k \leftarrow \mathcal{L}_E^k(u_t)$ Step 2. Update trigger memory (deterministic aggregation): $\mathcal{H}_t \leftarrow \mathcal{H}_{t-1} \oplus \tau_t$ Step 3. Compute module score, bands and confidence: $Score_k \leftarrow g_k(r^k)$; $\sigma_k^t, \tilde{s}_k^t \leftarrow f(Score_k)$ $C_k \leftarrow \frac{ \{i: r_i^k \neq \emptyset\} }{n_k}$ Step 3. Compute composite burden: $B_t = \sum_k w_k \times \tilde{s}_k^t$ Step 4. Compute distress index: $D_t = \gamma_B \times B_t^p + \gamma_T \times T_t + \gamma_{BT} \times B_t \times T_t$ Output: $X_{PA}^t = \{\mathcal{H}_t, \mathcal{M}_t, B_t, T_t, D_t\}$, where $\mathcal{M}_t = \{Score_k, C_k, \sigma_k, \tilde{s}_k^t\}$</p>
<p>3. Trend & Predictive Analyst (TPA) Input: utterance u_t, weights β, λ, distress index D_t, academic load index A_t, horizon h, thresholds θ_T, θ_D, weights l Step 1. Update smoothed distress index: $\bar{D}_t = \beta \times \bar{D}_{t-1} + (1 - \beta) \times clip(D_t \times (1 + \lambda \times A_t), 0, 1)$ Step 2. Compute trend slope: $\Delta \bar{D}_t = \bar{D}_t - \bar{D}_{t-h}$ Step 3. Determine trend label: IF $\Delta \bar{D}_t \geq \theta_T$ THEN $Trend_t \leftarrow$ worsening ELSE IF $\Delta \bar{D}_t \leq -\theta_T$ THEN $Trend_t \leftarrow$ improving ELSE $Trend_t \leftarrow$ stable END IF END IF Step 4. Extract linguistic severity: $L_t = l_1 \times E(u_t) + l_2 \times C(u_t) + l_3 \times S(u_t)$ Step 5. Compute warning flag: IF $D_t \geq \theta_D$ OR $\Delta \bar{D}_t \geq \theta_T$ AND $\Delta \bar{D}_{t-1} \geq \theta_T$ OR $L_t > \theta_L$ THEN $W_t \leftarrow 1$ ELSE $W_t \leftarrow 0$ END IF Output: $X_{TPA}^t = \{\bar{D}_t, \Delta \bar{D}_t, Trend_t, W_t, L_t\}$</p>
<p>4. Advisor Specialist (AS) Input: utterance u_t, risk level R_t, severity bands σ_k, active trigger τ_t, linguistic score L_t, LLM configuration \mathcal{L}_k^t Construct enhanced query: $Q_t^{enhanced} = u_t \oplus R_t \oplus \sum_{k \in M_k^t} \psi_k(\sigma_k, \tau_t, L_t)$ Output: Generate grounded response: $X_{AS}^t = \mathcal{L}_k^t(S_t, \mathcal{D}_k, Q_t^{enhanced})$</p>
<p>5. Differential Pattern Analyst (DPA)</p>

Input: state S_t , weights ω , calibration coefficient ρ
Step 1. For each symptom pattern k compute pattern score:
 $P_k^t \leftarrow 0$
FOR $i = 1$ TO 6:
 Compute $f_i(S_t)$
 $P_k^t \leftarrow P_k^t + \omega_i \times f_i(S_t)$
END FOR
 $P_k^t \leftarrow \rho \times P_k^t$
 $\mathcal{P}_t \leftarrow \{P_k^t\}$
Output: $X_{DPA}^t = \{\mathcal{P}_t\}$

3.3 Safety & orchestration layer

3.3.1 Risk Stratification Agent (RSA)

The RSA acts as the system's primary safety control mechanism, operating as a deterministic supervisory layer that precedes and constrains all downstream decision-making. Its role is to continuously evaluate both structured psychological indicators and linguistic risk signals to determine whether standard conversational support is appropriate or whether safety-oriented intervention must be activated. The agent implements a risk scoring function $\mathcal{T}_{Risk}(S_t) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ that evaluates the risk level $R_t \in \{0,1,2,3\}$.

The low risk is triggered when both distress index and linguistic severity index are below thresholds $\theta_{DM} = 0.15$ and $\theta_L = 0.6$:

$$\mathcal{T}_{Low}(S_t) = 1 \text{ if } (D_t < \theta_{DM}) \wedge (L_t < \theta_L) \quad (29)$$

The medium risk is triggered when D_t exceeds θ_{DM} but is lower than the high-risk level $\theta_{DH} = 0.3$ and L_t is still below threshold θ_L :

$$\mathcal{T}_{Medium}(S_t) = 1 \text{ if } (\theta_{DM} \leq D_t < \theta_{DH}) \wedge (L_t < \theta_L) \quad (30)$$

The high risk is triggered when either one module is at severe/high level or D_t exceeds threshold θ_{DH} or L_t is greater than linguistic threshold:

$$\mathcal{T}_{High}(S_t) = 1 \text{ if } (\max_k \sigma_k = 3) \vee (\theta_{DH} \leq D_t < \theta_{DC}) \vee (L_t > \theta_L) \quad (31)$$

where $\theta_{DC} = 0.5$ for safety screening indicating high risk.

Crisis escalation or the critical risk is triggered either by explicit self-harm language containing explicit high-risk linguistic signals (e.g., presence of suicide ideation or self-harm intent indicators) or by exceeding the distress threshold $\theta_{DC} = 0.5$, whichever occurs first.

$$\mathcal{T}_{Critical}(u_t, S_t) = 1 \Leftrightarrow (L_{suicide}(u_t) = 1) \vee (L_{selfharm}(u_t) = 1) \vee (D_t \geq \theta_{DC}) \quad (32)$$

If critical risk is triggered, then the policy is to activate the psychologist's dashboard and trigger an alert for an emergency action. Thus, the decision function of RSA can be expressed compactly as:

$$R_t = \begin{cases} 0 & \mathcal{T}_{Low}(S_t) = 1 \\ 1 & \mathcal{T}_{Medium}(S_t) = 1 \\ 2 & \mathcal{T}_{High}(S_t) = 1 \\ 3 & \mathcal{T}_{Critical}(u_t, S_t) = 1 \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

where 0→normal routing for LOW risk; 1→normal routing for MEDIUM risk; 2→safety screening for HIGH risk; 3→immediate escalation override for CRITICAL risk.

The risk levels are incorporated in the AS for query enhancement. In case risk level is high, the PA and TPA are scheduled for daily screening, and in case risk level is critical the RSA triggers alerts for psychologist intervention and prevent normal routing. Risk stratification is rule-based and threshold-deterministic rather than probabilistic, ensuring auditability and preventing under-escalation in high-distress states.

3.3.2 Orchestrator

The *Orchestrator* serves as the central policy agent that coordinates the activation and sequencing of cognitive agents based on the current state. It transforms the multidimensional state vector S_t into a structured action set, selecting which agents should be executed at each conversational step. It operates strictly downstream of the RSA, meaning that all routing decisions are conditioned on prior safety

validation. Formally, the *Orchestrator* implements a routing policy π that maps the state space to a subset of available agents $\mathcal{A}(S_t)$:

$$\pi(S_t) = \begin{cases} \mathcal{A}_{PA} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_{AS} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_{TPA} & u_t = \emptyset \vee \Delta C_t < \theta_C \\ \mathcal{A}_{AS} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_{TPA} & u_t \neq \emptyset \wedge R_t \in \{0,1\} \\ \mathcal{A}_{PA} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_{TPA}, \mathcal{A}_{AS} & u_t \neq \emptyset \wedge (R_t = 2 \vee W_t = 1) \\ \mathcal{A}_{ECA}, \mathcal{A}_{DPA} & \text{daily} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

The pseudocode of the RSA and *Orchestrator* is expressed in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2. Risk stratification and orchestration
<p>Input: User utterance u_t, academic context E_t Output: Updated state S_t, agent \mathcal{A}_t, system response \mathcal{O}_t</p> <p>Step 1. Initialization $R_0 \leftarrow 0; S_0 \leftarrow \{\}; \mathcal{H}_t \leftarrow \{\}$ $\mathcal{A}_{ECA}, \mathcal{A}_{PA}, \mathcal{A}_{TPA} \leftarrow \pi(S_0, R_0)$ Set state $S_0 \leftarrow f(X_{ECA}^0, X_{PA}^0, X_{TPA}^0)$</p> <p>Step 2. Manage interactions with Risk Stratification Agent (RSA) and Orchestrator WHILE $u_t \neq \emptyset$ LOOP IF $D_t < \theta_{DM}$ OR $L_t < \theta_L$ THEN $T_{LowRisk}(S_t) \leftarrow 1$ $R_t \leftarrow 0$ $\mathcal{A}_{AS}, \mathcal{A}_{TPA} \leftarrow \pi(S_t, R_t)$ Update state $S_t \leftarrow f(X_{AS}^t, X_{TPA}^t, R_t)$ ELSE IF $\theta_{DM} \leq D_t < \theta_{DH}$ OR $L_t < \theta_L$ THEN $T_{MediumRisk}(S_t) \leftarrow 1$ $R_t \leftarrow 1$ $\mathcal{A}_{AS}, \mathcal{A}_{TPA} \leftarrow \pi(S_t, R_t)$ Update state $S_t \leftarrow f(X_{AS}^t, X_{TPA}^t, R_t)$ ELSE IF $\max_k \sigma_k = 3$ OR $\theta_{DH} \leq D_t < \theta_{DC}$ OR $L_t > \theta_L$ THEN $T_{HighRisk}(S_t) = 1$ $R_t \leftarrow 2$ $\mathcal{A}_{AS}, \mathcal{A}_{TPA} \leftarrow \pi(S_t, R_t)$ Schedule daily $\mathcal{A}_{PA}, \mathcal{A}_{TPA}$ Update state $S_t \leftarrow f(X_{AS}^t, X_{AP}^t, X_{TPA}^t, R_t)$ ELSE IF $L_{suicide}(u_t) = 1$ OR $L_{selfharm}(u_t) = 1$ OR $D_t \geq \theta_{DC}$ THEN $T_{CrisisOverride}(u_t, S_t) = 1$ $R_t \leftarrow 3$ Update state $S_t \leftarrow f(R_t)$ Trigger emergency override (S_t) BREAK END IF Save state S_t END LOOP</p> <p>Step 3. Determine patterns for clinicians $\mathcal{A}_{DPA} \leftarrow \pi(S_t, R_t)$ Update state $S_t \leftarrow f(X_{DPA}^t)$</p> <p>Output: system response $\mathcal{O}_t \leftarrow \{S_t\}$</p>

4. Simulations

To evaluate the correctness, consistency and clinical plausibility of the proposed framework, we conducted a structured simulation study comprising 400 cases collected from voluntary testing interactions during February 2025 and January 2026, spanning 2 semesters and 2 exams periods. Each case is identified by a user id and contains multiple conversations and up to 4 consultations with PA and TPA. The dataset is evenly distributed across four severity levels (low, medium, high, critical) and four psychological modules (anxiety, stress, sleep disturbance and social anxiety), enabling controlled assessment of boundary behavior and escalation logic.

The evaluation reflects the modular multi-agent architecture of the system, with each agent assessed independently and in coordinated operation. Each agent is evaluated using task-specific metrics aligned with its functional objective (e.g., score consistency, threshold enforcement, calibration, retrieval performance, grounding and safety compliance). The simulation evaluates architectural coherence and internal safety logic rather than clinical outcome effectiveness, which will be addressed in future pilot studies.

4.1. Using natural language to profile students with PA through questionnaire-based conversations

Instead of presenting rigid survey forms, the PA leverages conversational dialogue to infer responses aligned with standardized screening instruments for each psychological mode. Extraction is performed by a LLM guided by a structured YAML prompt executed using *gemini-2.5-flash* which defines the system role and extraction constraints, topic-level validation strategies and a strict JSON output schema per module (see Supplementary material).

The PA operates in three distinct modes: i) *Consultant* generates conversational responses while tracking topic coverage without persisting state. A temperature of 0.3 balances empathetic tone with task orientation; ii) *Reviewer* applies deterministic extraction (temperature = 0.0), reviewing the full conversation and generating a structured profile patch, which is merged into the user state; iii) *Validator* identifies missing critical fields and reports completion status before score computation. After validation, the PA computes psychometric scores, severity bands, trigger burden index, composite burden index, distress index and updates the user state accordingly.

To evaluate the LLM extraction accuracy, the following metrics are computed as in Table 3: *Profile Completeness Rate (PCR)* measures the proportion of sessions where all critical questionnaire fields are successfully extracted; *Question Efficiency Ratio (QER)* measures the efficiency of conversational extraction; *Redundancy Rate (RR)* measures repetitive questioning.

Table 3. PA evaluation metrics

Metric	Formula	Results
Profile Completeness Rate (PCR)	$PCR = \frac{\#\{\text{complete profiles}\}}{\#\{\text{profiling sessions}\}}$	98%
Question Efficiency Ratio (QER)	$QER = \frac{\#\{\text{profiling topics covered}\}}{\#\{\text{questions asked}\}}$	1.3
Redundancy Rate (RR)	$RR = \frac{\#\{\text{questions targeting already covered topics}\}}{\#\{\text{questions asked}\}}$	2%

A 98% completeness rate indicates that the LLM consistently extracts structured psychometric data from natural conversations, while QER greater than 1 reflects efficient information gain per question, highlighting conversational compression. The 2% redundancy shows minimal repeated probing.

4.2 Computing trends and patterns using TPA and DPA agents

Since the TPA integrates structured questionnaire scores with deterministic linguistic signals extracted from conversations, evaluation focuses on (i) coverage of extracted linguistic features and (ii) consistency between language-derived severity and quantitative distress. The following metrics are computed:

- *Linguistic Feature Activation Rate (LFAR)* measures the fraction of conversation windows in which at least one feature within the family is activated above threshold. The metric evaluates linguistic coverage and ensures that the extractor produces meaningful signals across sessions. For each linguistic feature family F (emotional, cognitive, severity, domain), let us denote by $s_f(u_t) \in [0,1]$ the normalized score of the feature $f \in F$. Given an activation threshold θ_F , the LFAR is defined as:

$$LFAR(\theta_F) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N 1(\max s_f(u_t) \geq \theta_F) \quad (35)$$

- *Lexicon Signal Density (LSD)* assesses the feature selectivity and sparsity and quantifies the average proportion of activated features within each linguistic family. Low-to-moderate density values indicate selective triggering rather than indiscriminate lexical activation.

$$LSD(u_t; \theta_F) = \frac{1}{|F|} \sum_{f \in F} 1_{\theta_F}(f, u_t) \quad (36)$$

where $1_{\theta_F}(f, u_t) = \begin{cases} 1, & s_f(u_t) \geq \theta_F \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$.

The dataset-level density is then computed as:

$$\overline{LSD}(\theta_F) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N LSD(u_t; \theta_f) \quad (37)$$

- *Quantitative–Linguistic Consistency Score (QLCS)* evaluates whether language-derived severity aligns with the smoothed distress index trajectory.

$$QLCS(t) = 1 - |L(u_t) - \bar{D}_t| \quad (38)$$

and averaged over all windows:

$$QLCS = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N (1 - |L(u_t) - \bar{D}_t|) \quad (39)$$

Using an activation threshold $\theta_F = 0.4$ over $N = 1000$ conversations form the test cases, the emotional markers activated in 48.7% ($LFAR = 0.487$, $\overline{LSD} = 0.139$), while cognitive distortion features showed slightly higher activation and density ($LFAR = 0.505$, $\overline{LSD} = 0.214$), indicating frequent presence of distortion-related language in student discourse. Domain-specific markers activated in 49.7% of conversations ($LFAR=0.497$, $\overline{LSD} = 0.128$), supporting contextual routing without influencing severity estimation. In contrast, severity-indicator features activated less frequently ($LFAR = 0.253$, $\overline{LSD} = 0.084$), consistent with their expected lower prevalence. Across families, density values remained low-to-moderate (0.084–0.214), indicating selective triggering rather than lexical over-activation. Internal coherence between linguistic and quantitative modalities is high, with an average $QLCS = 0.873$, indicating the alignment between language-derived severity and the smoothed distress index, supporting the role of linguistic features as a stable augmentation mechanism within the multi-agent framework.

Across longitudinal simulations using TPA, the smoothed distress index exhibited stable dynamic behavior without oscillatory amplification, spanning the full operational range (0–50%) with a mean of approximately 23%, remaining below the early-warning threshold (30%) for most cases (Figure 2). The distribution shows no saturation at upper bounds, indicating that nonlinear burden scaling preserves high-severity separation without inflating moderate distress and confirms stable calibration and controlled sensitivity of the TPA trajectory model.

Figure 2. Distribution of smoothed distress index

Pattern analysis of the users shows predominance of social anxiety–dominant and stress overload hypotheses, consistent with typical university populations (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Pattern distribution

Above-threshold rates and boxplot distributions confirm graded activation rather than inflated scoring, with most pattern scores remaining within mild-to-moderate ranges. It confirms the DPA’s role as a differential hypothesis generator rather than a diagnostic classifier.

4.3. Identifying high and critical risks with RSA

The evaluation of the RSA constitutes a functional and calibration validation of the framework rather than a diagnostic assessment. The objective is to verify internal consistency, threshold enforcement, mathematical correctness and safety rule integrity under controlled simulation conditions. No clinical diagnostic claims are made. Instead, validation assesses whether the nonlinear scaling, smoothing operations and risk-mapping rules behave deterministically and coherently across predefined severity strata.

The validation is performed using an LLM-as-a-judge framework with GPT5.2 operationalized through a structured evaluation prompt defining explicit PASS/FAIL criteria. The judge assessed: *i)* alignment between severity bands and computed scores; *ii)* correct enforcement of clinical cutoffs (GAD-7, PSS-10, ISI, SPIN); *iii)* correctness of mathematical transformations (normalization, burden metrics, nonlinear distress scaling, smoothing); *iv)* appropriateness of risk stratification boundaries.

The results confirm consistent monotonic progression across severity strata. Average smoothed distress increases systematically from 4.1% (minimal) to 39.0% (severe), while the composite burden index rises from 9.9% to 21.2%. It demonstrates that the nonlinear burden scaling and distress formulation preserve separation between severity tiers without compression effects. Risk stratification shows clinically coherent escalation. Minimal and mild cases are classified exclusively as LOW risk, moderate cases as MEDIUM and severe cases largely as HIGH with a subset reaching CRITICAL. No severe case is assigned LOW/MEDIUM risk and no minimal case escalates to HIGH or CRITICAL, satisfying safety-critical validation constraints.

Modules-specific cutoff validation indicated correct enforcement of instrument thresholds (GAD-7 ≥ 10 ; PSS-10 ≥ 20 ; ISI ≥ 15 ; Mini-SPIN ≥ 12). Flag rates increased proportionally with simulated severity across all domains, confirming accurate integration of psychometric scoring within the RSA framework.

Based on the structured evaluation criteria, the LLM-as-a-judge issued a PASS verdict for the 400-case simulation. The RSA satisfies all predefined criteria: no arithmetic or structural computation errors detected; monotonic severity progression maintained; no safety-critical misclassifications; proper enforcement of risk thresholds; correct application of clinical cutoffs across instruments.

A band-consistency calibration analysis is conducted to evaluate alignment between the continuous distress index and discrete risk categories (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Calibration curve

The calibration curve shows near-perfect stepwise transitions across predefined decision thresholds. All cases with distress <15% are classified as LOW risk (83/83), all cases with distress between 15–30% are classified as MEDIUM risk (60/60), all cases exceeding 30% are classified as HIGH risk (186/186) and all cases exceeding 50% are classified as CRITICAL (71/71). No boundary leakage is observed. Mean distress values per risk band demonstrates strong separation: LOW (4.46%), MEDIUM (22.02%), HIGH (38.82%), and CRITICAL (58.59%), with non-overlapping ranges.

4.4 Managing conversations with AS

The AS uses *gemini-2.5-flash* with *max_tokens=2048* and *temperature=0.1*. Embeddings are configured separately, with *Gemini text-embedding-004* with 3072 dimensions. The retrieval stack uses a FAISS vector index built over 120 PDFs files extracted from NHS self-help guides, NICE guides and university materials with chunk size of 2048 and overlap 300. At query time, retrieval is hybrid: dense semantic search is fused with BM25 signals, then a cross-encoder re-ranker is applied. The re-ranker model is set to *BAAI/bge-reranker-base*, and the pipeline keeps a larger first-stage candidate set before selecting the final top-K after reranking and neighbor expansion for context continuity.

The prompt system is defined in YAML and it constrains AS to non-diagnostic, supportive mental health guide that must draw only from retrieved context and explicitly avoid diagnosis, prescription or replacement of professional care. Safety constraints are enforced with an escalation trigger list (e.g., “suicidal”, “self-harm”, “crisis”), and a mandatory crisis protocol inserts emergency services. The prompt structure is intentionally rigid: it requires acknowledgment, evidence-based strategies, actionable steps, professional-help guidance and a supportive closing.

Dynamic personalization is incorporated through a user profile template (primary concern, emotional state, intensity, triggers, academic context, support availability). The system also injects topic-specific guidance (e.g., anxiety, stress, sleep, social anxiety), including suggested openings, focus areas and “avoid” lists to prevent unsafe language. The final user prompt embeds retrieved guidelines, the student’s question, and explicit response requirements to ensure grounded, safe and step-wise advice. Sample conversations are included in Supplementary material. The AS maintained domain consistency, provided evidence-based psychoeducational strategies, avoided diagnostic framing and adapted recommendations across evolving conversational themes (e.g., academic anxiety, parental expectations, relational stress), while preserving safety constraints.

The AS is evaluated under two complementary settings: *i*) an external robustness benchmark using the Psych8k¹ dataset and *ii*) a controlled internal benchmark constructed from 400-case simulation data.

¹ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/EmoCareAI/Psych8k>

The Psych8k dataset comprises 260 real counseling conversations with 8,000 question–answer interactions covering themes such as emotional regulation, family dynamics, relationships, career development and academic stress. As these transcripts do not contain questionnaire-derived user profiles, the baseline AS operates without psychometric or trigger-based query enhancement. This setting evaluates generalization and robustness under conversational variability.

The controlled internal benchmark consists of 1200 question–answer interactions extracted from 400 test cases. In this setting, two configurations are compared: a baseline agent using only the raw user query and an enhanced version in which the query is augmented with contextual information derived from the user profile (severity scores, trigger, risk level and composite burden index). The internal benchmark is designed to evaluate the performance gains attributable to query enhancement.

The following metrics are computed for each dataset:

a) *Retrieval effectiveness* is quantified using *Precision@k* ($k = 3$), *Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR)* and *nDCG@k* ($k = 3$), computed from the ranked list of retrieved sources. Response length is reported as an auxiliary descriptive metric (average characters per response).

b) *Generation quality* is evaluated along four dimensions:

- *Domain alignment* measures topic detection accuracy by comparing the detected domain to the gold domain label (anxiety, sleep, stress, social anxiety) in the internal benchmark. Accuracy is computed as a binary match per sample and averaged across cases.
- *Severity alignment* evaluates whether crisis detection behavior is appropriate for the internal benchmark. A score of 1.0 is assigned when no inappropriate crisis escalation occurs and 0.5 otherwise.
- *Safety compliance* assesses adherence to safety constraints (e.g., no diagnostic claims, no medication recommendations, appropriate phrasing). Responses receive a score of 1.0 when compliant and 0.5 when safety concerns are detected.
- *Groundedness* evaluates whether responses are supported by retrieved sources using the LLM-as-a-judge framework. Scores are assigned on a 0–2 scale (fully, partially or not grounded). The hallucination rate is reported as the proportion of responses receiving a groundedness score of 0.

Because the Psych8k dataset does not provide gold domain or severity annotations, domain alignment and severity alignment metrics are not computed in the external benchmark. Instead, evaluation on Psych8k focuses on retrieval effectiveness, groundedness, hallucination rate and safety compliance, providing an assessment of robustness under distributional shift rather than controlled alignment testing.

Table 4. Evaluation metrics of the Advisor

Metrics	Psych8k	Internal baseline	Internal enhanced
Retrieval metrics			
• Precision@3	0.53	0.56	0.72
• MRR	0.65	0.67	0.81
• nDCG@3	0.63	0.65	0.85
Generation metrics			
• Domain accuracy	-	60%	90%
• Severity score	-	1	1
• Safety score	1	1	1
• Groundedness	1	1	1.55
• Hallucination rate	25%	25%	12%

Table 4 shows that the baseline AS generalizes reasonably to the Psych8k benchmark (Precision@3=0.53, MRR=0.65, nDCG@3=0.63) with full safety compliance but moderate grounding (1.0) and a hallucination rate of 25%. On the controlled internal benchmark, augmenting the retrieval query with structured profile context substantially improves retrieval effectiveness (Precision@3: 0.56→0.72; MRR: 0.67→0.81; nDCG@3: 0.65→0.85) and generation quality (domain accuracy: 60%→90%; groundedness: 1.0→1.55), while reducing hallucinations (25%→12%) without affecting safety (score=1.0). The average response length for the baseline is 6808 characters while for the enhanced model it is 6909 characters. Table 5 compares baseline and enhanced query configurations across psychological modules.

Table 5. Comparison between the baseline and enhanced query configurations for each module

Module	Domain accuracy	Groundedness	Hallucination	MRR	Precision@3
Anxiety	80% → 90%	0.80 → 1.50	20% → 15%	0.76 → 0.80	0.70 → 0.80
Sleep	80% → 95%	0.80 → 1.60	40% → 10%	0.56 → 1.00	0.40 → 0.73
Stress	60% → 100%	1.20 → 1.40	40% → 10%	0.80 → 0.80	0.66 → 0.88
Social Anxiety	20% → 70%	1.20 → 1.60	20% → 13%	0.58 → 0.76	0.40 → 0.60

Query enhancement consistently improves retrieval ranking, groundedness and hallucination reduction without degrading safety. The largest gains are observed in sleep, stress and social anxiety, indicating that structured profile signals are particularly beneficial in domains with high lexical overlap or ambiguity.

5. Conclusions

This paper proposes SENTIA, a hierarchical, state-governed, risk-aware multi-agent architecture designed to address key limitations of current LLM-based mental health assistants. The framework is motivated by three research questions concerning deterministic orchestration (RQ1), persistent structured state modeling (RQ2) and formal risk stratification with crisis override (RQ3).

Regarding RQ1, we demonstrated that LLM-based systems can be architected within a deterministic supervisory paradigm by separating generative components from state-transition logic and embedding them within an auditable orchestration layer. The simulation results confirm stable and monotonic severity progression, absence of routing inconsistencies and zero safety-critical misclassifications across 400 structured cases. The LLM-as-a-judge validation issued a PASS verdict, supporting architectural coherence and deterministic threshold enforcement.

For RQ2, the introduction of a persistent psychometric-aligned state vector enabled longitudinal monitoring and structured burden modeling beyond prompt-driven conversational memory. The PA achieved a 98% profile completeness rate with minimal redundancy (2%), demonstrating that structured questionnaire-aligned extraction can be reliably reconstructed from natural dialogue. The TPA exhibited stable trajectory dynamics, with smoothed distress index spanning the operational range without oscillatory amplification and maintaining high quantitative–linguistic consistency.

Concerning RQ3, the RSA successfully operationalized explicit, rule-based crisis governance. Calibration analysis showed perfect boundary adherence across risk strata, with no boundary leakage and non-overlapping distress ranges between LOW, MEDIUM, HIGH, and CRITICAL levels. Severe cases are never under-escalated and minimal cases never over-escalated, confirming safety-critical determinism. The retrieval-augmented AS further demonstrated that structured profile-informed query enhancement significantly improves grounded generation. On the controlled benchmark, retrieval effectiveness increased (Precision@3: 0.56→0.72; nDCG@3: 0.65→0.85), domain accuracy improved (60%→90%) and hallucination rates decreased (25%→12%) without compromising safety compliance. These results indicate that integrating structured psychometric signals into retrieval conditioning enhances alignment and reduces generative drift.

From a methodological perspective, SENTIA advances LLM-based mental health systems from conversational assistance toward a state-centric, auditable and neuro-symbolic expert system paradigm. Rather than relying on probabilistic memory and prompt heuristics, the framework operationalizes deterministic supervisory control, structured longitudinal modeling, and formal safety governance. Although clinical outcome validation requires future real-world deployment studies, the present simulations confirm internal coherence, calibration stability, and safety rule integrity. SENTIA provides a transferable architectural blueprint for safety-critical LLM-based decision-support systems in higher education and beyond, reconciling generative flexibility with structured, interpretable and reproducible supervisory intelligence.

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